

Optimal Planning of Electrical Appliances and Photovoltaic Systems in Residential Complexes under Real Time Pricing Mechanism

By

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A Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of the Sirjan University of Technology
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Bachelor of Science in Electrical Engineering

Department of Electrical Engineering
Sirjan University of Technology

January 15, 2022

Abstract

Residential complexes (RCs) consisting of photovoltaic (PV) systems, wind turbines, and electric vehicles (EVs) have rapidly expanded in energy systems in recent years. Optimal planning of local production units can lead to economic improvement in RCs. In this regard, it seems necessary to optimize the performance of RCs. Operators of RC energy systems equipped with local generation units can take advantage of demand response programs (DRPs) to reduce their operating costs while meeting energy demand. In these programs, energy consumers are encouraged to change their consumption in such a way that economic goals are met.

In this paper, the optimal performance of a grid-connected PV/EV RC energy system under real-time pricing of a DRP is studied. The studied RC energy system is equipped with PV units and EVs, which can support RCs in meeting energy demand and providing economic benefits. The integrated PV unit is modeled by considering the parameters of solar radiation and ambient temperature, which can lead to accurate simulation results. In addition, the proposed model for EVs can increase the effective operation of RCs through optimal charging and discharging processes. In addition, the optimal operation of integrated energy systems in RCs is modeled as mixed integer linear programming (MILP). In addition, a General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS) is used to perform simulations in different scenarios and the results are presented for comparison. For the studied test, the total expected cost of RCs is reduced by 90.68%, which shows the effective impact of demand response on the optimal scheduling of DG units.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Introduction

Today, due to the crises caused by excessive consumption of fossil fuels, renewable energy sources such as wind turbines [1] [2] [3] and photovoltaic systems [4] [5] [3], (PV) They are widely used in power systems. These sources produce clean and cheap energy to meet energy needs. However, inconsistent production of these resources can cause many problems for energy system operators. In order to address these issues, electric vehicles [6] [7] [8] [9] [10] (EVs) can be integrated with other energy sources in power systems.

In this section, nets of studies on the exploitation of residential microgrid energy systems under the combination of distributed generation units (DG) in different fields are presented.

Renewable sources are among the most appropriate options for energy sources in microgrids. Different types of these resources are integrated in microgrids to fulfill different purposes. For example, the problem of energy management in microgrids consisting of solar and wind units, boilers, microturbines, CHP and energy storage systems under different loads was studied [11]. Furthermore, a residential microgrid containing a small-sized wind turbine and PV panels was managed using a new strategy to improve the grid power profile and reduce peak power [12].

In another study [13], various strategies were used to minimize the monthly energy bill of the University of California - San Diego by using renewable energy sources.

The implementation of the genetic algorithm, the unit commitment problem and the economic distribution problem of renewable units in microgrids were evaluated by [14]. In addition, the optimal energy management of microgrids was studied in order to reduce the total cost of purchasing electricity from various sources such as PV units, wind turbines, hydropower units, thermal units and gas-fired power generation systems [15]. In another work [16], the cost-effective performance of a PV-based residential microgrid energy system under feed-in tariff was investigated, where the payback index was used to evaluate the economic performance of the studied system.

Renewable-based microgrids can be stable enough to supply energy consumers in isolated/island operating modes. In reference [17], a distributed energy management method based on the method of alternating orientation of multipliers was implemented to optimize the performance of grid-connected/island PV-based microgrids under power flow limitations. In order to control the performance of an isolated microgrid that includes renewable energy sources, a robust technique to prevent frequency instabilities in probabilities was presented [18].

Microgrids may include different types of distributed energy resources (DERs), including renewable and non-renewable. In order to share the power between coupled DERs in an independent island microgrid under unbalanced loads, a robust control method was employed by [19].

In addition, the optimal design of hybrid power generation systems including renewable units such as PVs for isolated areas using meta-heuristic optimization techniques such as particle swarm optimization was achieved by [20].

The integration of renewable resources can lead to hybrid energy systems for various applications in power systems, especially in microgrids. Optimum planning and design of hybrid renewable energy systems for microgrid applications was obtained using the customer acceptance model of distributed energy resources in [21]. The authors in reference [22] presented a new model for replacing the internal combustion engine of vehicles with renewable units such as wind turbines and PV systems. In addition, in [23], the analysis of the performance of secondary distribution networks consisting of renewable microgrids was focused on solving problems related to the distribution network, such as voltage instabilities, power losses, etc.

Determining the optimal size and placement of renewable units in microgrids has also been considered in some researches. In this research, which was presented in [24], the problems of optimal placement of DG units, including renewable sources, were investigated in terms of different parameters such as the type of problem, the methods used, etc.

In reference [25] renewable energy production resources were optimally measured in a community microgrid using a new method based on the Markov model and combining the interior point algorithm.

Demand side management programs have been implemented in research papers to improve the performance of microgrids. By implementing two demand response programs (DRPs) based on time-of-use pricing and real-time pricing (RTP) in [26] optimal day-ahead scheduling of microgrids consisting of different types of renewable energy sources to minimize the total operating cost by using optimal Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) was studied [27]. Demand response packages were proposed as renewable uncertainty control options. In addition, multi-function two-level programming to minimize the energy cost of the distribution network operator with multiple assumptions. Microgrids and DRPs [28] were used. In addition, a multi-objective energy management system was presented, where microgrid performance was optimized in the presence of uncertainty of renewable units and demand response providers [29].

Demand response providers cover the uncertainty of wind units and PV systems. In this regard, the optimal component size of microgrids was obtained using DRP to balance the production and consumption of energy and peak load and minimize their cost [30] Similar issues have also been studied together with EV planning. . As one of the new technologies that are rapidly expanding in energy systems, especially in microgrids, EVs have been combined to improve the performance of microgrids by providing various services.

The effect of integrating different types of EVs with different features and renewable units in power systems was investigated. In order to address the optimal performance of microgrids in the presence of hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), robust optimization is applied to minimize the operating cost of microgrids while considering possible risks [31]. became. In [32], the

implementation of a new robust and symbiotic search algorithm (SOS) was evaluated for optimal energy management of microgrids including PHEVs, storage devices and renewable energy sources, where the total cost of the system covers local generation units as well as The interaction cost between the upstream network and the microgrid is minimized. By implementing a new optimization algorithm based on the Bat algorithm, the optimal planning of power units in renewable local distribution systems including PHEVs was studied, in which the total cost of the network includes the cost of unsupplied energy, the cost of reliability and the cost of providing electricity for Loads and PHEVs were minimized. By solving non-linear optimization, an optimal next-day operation plan for microgrids was obtained in order to reduce the operating cost of microgrids under the optimal integration of EVs and using vehicle-to-grid (G2V) technology. Similarly, G2V technology was used to improve the performance of microgrids in unbalanced and isolated modes.[33] It fulfills economic-environmental expectations and provides market opportunities by considering risks [34]. Placement and sizing of G2V technologies in a microgrid was studied by [35]. Areas where energy systems such as charging stations are installed play a key role in the operation of installed production units. To analyze a location from different perspectives, different factors must be considered and sufficient data from end users must be collected, which can be obtained through innovative data collection technologies [36]. In this regard, fast charging stations are optimally located to maximize long-distance travel completion in the United States. [37] It should be noted that with the advancement of technology, wireless charging technologies have been developed for EVs in recent years. , which is summarized in [38]. With the aim of charging EVs by renewable energy sources and increasing the export capacity, the potential of intelligent charging of EVs was analyzed in [39]. were developed, in which a new optimization framework consisting of two steps was developed to consider the power flow constraints while optimizing the charging power of EVs. For this purpose, first, the power flow constraints were evaluated and the optimal power supply for EVs was given. The penetration of EVs and the control of their charge and discharge patterns in power systems can be challenged by various issues such as random arrival times. Optimal load patterns for EVs were obtained through global and local planning schemes in reference [41]. In doing so, a comprehensive planning scheme was developed to minimize the total cost considering the pre-known EV arrivals. In addition, a local planning scheme was developed to minimize the total cost in the current EV fleet in The local group was developed. The results showed that the local planning scheme leads to closer optimization results.

Similarly, in reference [42] a unidirectional vehicle to grid technology was applied to supply energy and ancillary services to a power grid. According to the model presented in their study, consumers and utilities can have the best performance by taking advantage of the options provided. In another research, [43], a data-based non-parametric joint optimization model for economic distribution An optimal PV-based energy system was developed, where the uncertainty of the power generated by a PV system was considered through the proposed model.

In this paper, a mathematically based optimization framework for energy management of a residential complex (RC) in South Africa is presented, which includes a specific energy

consumption pattern. The mentioned RC is a grid-connected energy system, in which renewable generation units such as PV systems as well as storage technologies such as EVs are used in order to improve its performance from different perspectives.

PV systems can produce clean and cheap power to be used to supply load or export process. Accurate modeling of PV generation is essential to have realistic particle simulation results. Therefore, a mathematically based accurate model is proposed to formulate the output power of PV systems. EVs can manage energy consumption in RC by controlling the intermittent generation of PV systems through optimal charging and discharging processes. In fact, EVs can have two-way power exchange (charge/discharge) with RC, and the charge/discharge processes can help RC to optimize energy consumption and control the intermittent generation of PV systems. The power discharged by EVs can be used for Demand supply can be used during peak periods, which can reduce the negative economic impact of the power taken from the upstream grid in the mentioned periods. Similar to PV systems, a mathematical model is proposed to model the operation of EVs has been

In order to evaluate the performance of RC compared to DRPs, an RTP mechanism is proposed and the performance of RC is evaluated from different economic points of view. It should be noted that in order to optimize the performance of the energy system, various valuable methods have already been introduced, one of which is They were random constraint optimization method. This method is mainly used to solve optimization problems considering possible conditions [44]. At first, different scenarios are generated with different probabilities for uncertain parameters, and then according to this method, the probability of meeting a certain constraint is guaranteed [45].

The main focus of the proposed mathematical model is on the optimal integration of renewable energy sources such as PV units as well as storage facilities such as EVs in RC systems that may include energy demand with different patterns. Furthermore, the proposed model seeks to assess the impact of DRPs such as RTP on the economic performance of RCs in countries such as South Africa.

Therefore, the results of the study can be stated as follows:

Optimum exploitation of a renewable RC according to the real data of Durba city in South Africa;

Using EVs to control the intermittent generation of PV systems and obtain economic benefits;

Implementation of RTP to improve RC performance by reducing total operating cost;

Proposing a comprehensive optimization framework based on MILP for optimal energy management and uncertainty management in a grid-connected RC with a local energy unit.

Other sections of the implemented article are classified as follows: Mathematical formulas are presented in section 2. Simulations and related results are presented in Section 3. Finally, the results are presented in Section 4.

Chapter 2: Problem formulation

The proposed optimization model is mathematically formulated in this section for the economic performance of a grid-connected RC including PV and EV system with RTP.

2.1 Objective function

As the objective function, the total cost of RC including the cost of electricity imported from RC minus the income from electricity given to the upstream network should be minimized in equation (1).

$$Min, obj = cost = \left(\sum_S^{SN} \Pi_S \times \sum_t^T \left(P_{t,s}^{imp} \times \lambda_t^{imp} - P_{t,s}^{exp} \times \lambda_t^{exp} \right) \right) \times TP \quad (1)$$

where obj is the objective function, cost is the total operation cost of RC, SN is the number of scenarios, s is the scenario index, T is the scheduling horizon, t is the time period, $P_{t,s}^{imp}$ is the imported power from the upstream grid, λ_t^{imp} is the price of power imported from the upstream grid, $P_{t,s}^{exp}$ is power exported to the upstream grid λ_t^{exp} is the price of power exported to the upstream grid and TP is the number of scheduling days.

2.2 Energy balance constraint

The required power for critical and non-critical loads is received from the output power of the PV system, the upstream grid and the discharge power of the EV. The mentioned explanations are mathematically modeled in Eq. (2).

$$P_{t,s}^{load,C} + P_{t,s}^{load,Nc} = P_{t,s}^{pv} + P_{t,s}^{imp} - P_{t,s}^{exp} + P_{t,s}^{dchev} - P_{t,s}^{chev} \quad (2)$$

where $P_{t,s}^{load,C}$ is the critical load, $P_{t,s}^{load,Nc}$ is the non-critical load, $P_{t,s}^{chev}$ is the charge power of the EV, $P_{t,s}^{pv}$ is the output power of the PV system and $P_{t,s}^{dchev}$ is the discharge power of the EV.

2.3 Limitations of distributed generation unit (DG)

In this section, the limits of DG and EV units are presented through equations (3) - (13).

2.3.1 Photovoltaic (PV) system

Renewable units such as PV systems can play a positive role in the optimal utilization of energy systems. The power produced by these systems is usually intermittent. Therefore, accurate modeling of these units is essential for accurate simulation results. The proposed model for the PV system in this paper is a comprehensive mathematical model taken from [16], based on which the output of the PV system is proportional to solar radiation, cell temperature, the number of PV panels in series and parallel, and other related factors. The proposed model is expressed in equations (3) - (5) (Nomibi and Malinga 2017).

$$P_{t,s}^{pv} = P_{stc}^{pv} \times n_{se}^{pv} \times n_{pa}^{pv} \times I_{d,s} \times \cos \theta_{\beta} + I_{dif,s} \times \frac{(1 + \cos \beta)}{2} + \rho \times I_{g,s} \times \frac{(1 - \cos \theta_{\beta})}{1000} \quad (3)$$

$$\times (1 - \alpha \times (T_{t,s}^c - 25))$$

where P_{stc}^{pv} is the PV output at the maximum power point and the standard test condition, P_{se}^{pv} is the number of PV panels in series, P_{pa}^{pv} is the number of PV panels in parallel, $I_{d,s}$ is the direct normal irradiance, θ_{β} is the incidence angle of solar radiation on a tilted surface, $I_{dif,s}$ is the diffuse horizontal irradiance, β is the tilted angle, ρ is the surrounding reflection, $I_{g,s}$ is the global horizontal irradiance, α is the temperature coefficient of the PV system and $T_{t,s}^c$ is the temperature of cells. The temperature of cells mentioned above is proportional to the ambient temperature, which is expressed in Eq. (4).

$$T_{t,s}^c = T_{t,s}^a + I_{d,s} \times \cos \theta_{\beta} + I_{dif,s} \times \frac{(1 + \cos \beta)}{2} + \rho \times I_{g,s} \times \frac{(1 - \cos \theta_{\beta})}{2 \times 800} \quad (4)$$

$$\times (NOCT - 20)$$

Where $T_{t,s}^a$ is the ambient temperature and NOCT is the nominal temperature of the operating cell.

The output power of the PV system must be within the legal range as follows:

$$P_{t,s}^{pv} \leq P_{t,max}^{mppt} \quad (5)$$

where $P_{t,max}^{mppt}$ is the maximum power of the converter.

2.3.2 electric vehicle model

Integrated EV is modeled through equations (6) - (13). EVs can optimally charge and discharge power to optimize energy consumption in RCs. However, there are limitations such as the availability of EVs, charging and discharging rates, etc. that need to be considered in modeling such energy units. According to its availability, the total load power of EV should be less than the allowed load amount which is expressed in equation (6). In addition, the EV discharge power in the current period is limited to less than the nominal discharge rate, which is expressed in Equation (7).

Finally, when EV is available, charging and discharging processes should not occur simultaneously, which is expressed in Equation (8).

$$P_{t,s}^{chev} \leq P_{\max}^{chev} \times B_{t,s}^{ch} \times M_t \quad (6)$$

Where $P_{t,s}^{chev}$ is the charging power of the EV, P_{\max}^{chev} is the maximum charge power of the EV, $B_{t,s}^{ch}$ is the binary variable of the EV charging condition and M_t is the availability of the EV.

$$P_{t,s}^{dchev} \leq P_{\max}^{dchev} \times B_{t,s}^{dch} \times M_t \quad (7)$$

Where $P_{t,s}^{dchev}$ is the discharge power of the EV, P_{\max}^{dchev} is the maximum discharge power of the EV and $B_{t,s}^{dch}$ is the binary variable of the EV discharging condition.

$$B_{t,s}^{ch} + B_{t,s}^{dch} \leq M_t \quad (8)$$

The state of charge (SOC) of the EV at present hour depends on SOC in previous hour and charge and discharge processes. The SOC of the EV is mathematically expressed in Eq. (9)

$$SOC_{t,s} = SOC_{t-1,s} + P_{t,s}^{chev} \times \eta_t^{chev} - \frac{P_{t,s}^{dchev}}{\eta_t^{dchev}} \quad (9)$$

where $SOC_{t,s}$ is the SOC of the EV, η_t^{chev} is the rate of charge of the EV and η_t^{dchev} is the rate of discharge of the EV.

The SOC of the EV is limited by Eq. (10).

$$SOC_{\min} \leq SOC_{t,s} \leq SOC_{\max} \quad (10)$$

where SOC_{\min} and SOC_{\max} are the minimum and maximum SOC of the EV, respectively.

The limitations related to the SOC of the EV at arrival and departure time are expressed in Eqs.(11)e(13). It is worth mentioning that in order to consider different driving patterns, the scenariobased methodology is utilized to generate scenarios in order to model the stochastic nature of the SOC value at the arrival time of the EV.

$$SOC_{t,s}^{Arive} \leq SOC_{\max}^{Arive} \quad (11)$$

where $SOC_{t,s}^{Arive}$ is the SOC of the EV at arrival time and SOC_{\max}^{Arive} is the maximum SOC of the EV at arrival time.

$$SOC_{t,s}^{Dep} \leq SOC_{desired}^{Dep} \quad (12)$$

$$SOC_{desired}^{Dep} = SOC_{\max} \quad (13)$$

where $SOC_{t,s}^{Dep}$ is the SOC of the EV at departure time and $SOC_{desired}^{Dep}$ is the desired SOC of the EV at departure time

2.3.3 upstream network

The power given from the RC network to the upstream network and the power input from the upstream network to the RC network are limited by equations 14 and 15. According to equation (14), the given total power cannot exceed the rated power of the RC connection line to the upstream network.

In addition, as stated in equation (15), the total power taken should be within the nominal range of the line. Finally, equation (16) is used to limit the simultaneous power input and output.

Therefore, according to equation (16), the processes of taking and giving power cannot occur simultaneously.

$$I_{t,s}^{exp} \times P_{min}^{exp} \leq P_{t,s}^{exp} \leq I_{t,s}^{exp} \times P_{max}^{exp} \quad (14)$$

where $I_{t,s}^{exp}$ is the binary variable for power export and, P_{max}^{exp} and P_{min}^{exp} are, respectively, the maximum and minimum power exported to the upstream grid.

$$I_{t,s}^{imp} \times P_{min}^{imp} \leq P_{t,s}^{imp} \leq I_{t,s}^{imp} \times P_{max}^{imp} \quad (15)$$

where $I_{t,s}^{imp}$ is the binary variable for power import and, P_{max}^{imp} and P_{min}^{imp} are, respectively, the maximum and minimum power imported from the upstream grid.

$$I_{t,s}^{exp} + I_{t,s}^{imp} \leq 1 \quad (16)$$

2.3.4 Real-time pricing mechanism (RTP)

At some hours during the day, due to the peak electricity consumption, the price of electricity increases and as a result, the total cost of energy consumption increases proportionally in the mentioned periods. An option to manage energy consumption during such periods is DRPs.

DRPs can help consumers manage their consumption more effectively to lower their payments. In this paper, RTP and DRP are used, which enable consumers to modify their consumption pattern according to predetermined energy rates.

RTP is formulated in equation (17).

$$P_{DRP,t,s}^{load,NC} = P_{t,s}^{load,NC} + E \times P_{t,s}^{load,NC} \times \frac{(\lambda_t^{imp} - RT_t^{price})}{RT_t^{price}} \quad (17)$$

where $P_{DRP,t,s}^{load.NC}$ is the non-critical load under RTP, E is the demandprice elasticity coefficient ($[-0.5, 0]$) and RT_t^{price} is the real-time power price.

Chapter 3: Numerical study

In this section, the optimal performance of PV-based RC under EV implementation is numerically studied without and with RTP. The studied RC is shown in Figure 1. The proposed problem is modeled as a MILP and GAMS software is used to solve it [46].

Figure (1) RC based on PV-EV studied

3.1 Input data

The input data required to run the simulations are given below:

Necessary and non-essential load profiles, real-time and upstream network price, solar radiation and ambient temperature of PV system, technical data of PV system and upstream network technical parameters are taken from [16]. In addition, technical data related to EV and EV availability for charging and discharging processes are taken from previous studies [47]. The probability of each scenario and the value of uncertainty parameters in each scenario are presented.

3.2 Results

In this section, the simulations are performed and the expected values of the result in different cases are presented. According to the obtained results, without considering the RTP, the total expected operating cost of the RC in the defined horizon is \$130,394, which includes the cost of \$866,490 of electricity taken from the upstream grid and \$736,096 of electricity income. In order to motivate energy consumers to revise their energy consumption pattern, RTP is used from DRP. Therefore, considering this type of pricing, the total expected operating cost of the RC over the defined horizon is \$12,144, which includes the \$196,324 cost of electricity imported from the upstream grid and the \$506,248 revenue earned from the electricity given to the upstream grid. From the obtained results, it is clear that by implementing RTP from DRP, the total expected cost of RC is reduced to 90.68%. In fact, with the efficient charging and discharging processes of EV system with RTP, the economic goals of RC are more satisfactory, which seems to be suitable for RC. For further comparison, numerical results without and with RTP from DRP are presented in Table 9. Also, the total cost of RC, including the cost of purchasing electricity from the upstream network and the income from selling electricity to the upstream network, is shown in Figure 2. The redundant demand with RTP from DRP is shown in Figure 3. According to this figure, the energy consumption pattern changes with RTP in a way to reduce the total RC payouts.

Numerical optimization results (objective function) without and with RTP

	Unit	Value	
		Without RTP	With RTP
Total expected cost	\$	130.394	12.144
Import cost	\$	866.490	196.324
Export revenue	\$	736.096	506.248
Total cost reduction	%		90.68

Figure (2) Total cost of RC with details without and with RTP

Figure (3) Unnecessary demand with RTP

The total power taken from the upstream network is shown in Figure 4. Based on this figure, the power input from the upstream network decreases with RTP; Therefore, the total cost of RC is

reduced. In addition, as shown in Figure 5, the total transmitted power from the RC to the upstream network increases with RTP, which leads to more benefits.

Figure (4) Power imported from the upstream network

Figure (5) power given to the upstream network

The charging and discharging rates of EV without and with RTP are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. As shown in these figures, the EV is optimally charged and discharged with RTP to balance the alternating output of the PV system and the supply energy demand.

Figure (6) EV charging power

Figure (7) EV discharge power

Chapter 4: Conclusion

Residential complexes include energy units such as EV and PV that are accurately modeled and can exchange energy with upstream grids to gain benefits. Different types of DG units can be integrated into RCs to meet the energy needs with their local production. In this paper, a mathematical-based optimization framework for optimal integration of a PV unit and an EV in a grid-connected RC is presented. In which the used energy units were modeled through precise mathematical models so that the simulation results are as accurate as possible. In addition, the RTP demand response mechanism is implemented to improve the economic performance of the system and consumer behavior towards the proposed prices. It has been analyzed in the mentioned mechanism.

According to the simulation results, the proposed models for energy units are optimally configured in RC and the optimal economic operation of RC is obtained. In addition, the power generated by the PV unit was effectively used to meet the energy demand and EV charging, and the stored energy was used for export or to meet the demand. It should be noted that various scenarios have been developed to model the random driving patterns at the time of EV arrival, and it can be seen that the income from the export of excess electricity produced by the PV unit can provide economic benefits for the RC.

After applying RTP, the discussed economic results increased since the total expected cost of RC operation under the RTP mechanism was reduced by 90.68%, which shows the optimal performance of energy units integrated in RC with RTP. Energy units including PV systems and EVs with RTP can operate more efficiently, which can lead to a reduction in the total cost of RC operations.

It should be noted that the amount of numerical results obtained, such as the percentage of cost savings, depends on the test system

The proposed mathematical model is easily applicable to other cases and can be extended to other systems with different energy mixtures. Through the extension of the proposed model, the probabilistic performance of RC can be evaluated using different methodologies such as the chance constraint method in future works.

References

- [1] H. Fathabadi, "Novel standalone hybrid solar/wind/fuel cell power generation system for remote areas," *Solar Energy*, vol. 146, pp. 30-43, 2017/04/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.01.071>.
- [2] M. A. Mirzaei, A. S. Yazdankhah, B. Mohammadi-Ivatloo, M. Marzband, M. Shafie-khah, and J. P. S. Catalão, "Stochastic network-constrained co-optimization of energy and reserve products in renewable energy integrated power and gas networks with energy storage system," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 223, pp. 747-758, 2019/06/20/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.021>.
- [3] S. A. Shezan *et al.*, "Performance analysis of an off-grid wind-PV (photovoltaic)-diesel-battery hybrid energy system feasible for remote areas," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 125, pp. 121-132, 2016/07/01/ 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.03.014>.
- [4] A. L. Bukar and C. W. Tan, "A review on stand-alone photovoltaic-wind energy system with fuel cell: System optimization and energy management strategy," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 221, pp. 73-88, 2019/06/01/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.228>.
- [5] M. Majidi, S. Nojavan, N. Nourani Esfetanaj, A. Najafi-Ghalelou, and K. Zare, "A multi-objective model for optimal operation of a battery/PV/fuel cell/grid hybrid energy system using weighted sum technique and fuzzy satisfying approach considering responsible load management," *Solar Energy*, vol. 144, pp. 79-89, 2017/03/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.01.009>.
- [6] P. Aliasghari, B. Mohammadi-Ivatloo, M. Alipour, M. Abapour, and K. Zare, "Optimal scheduling of plug-in electric vehicles and renewable micro-grid in energy and reserve markets considering demand response program," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 186, pp. 293-303, 2018/06/10/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.058>.
- [7] H. Fathabadi, "Novel battery/photovoltaic hybrid power source for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles," *Solar Energy*, vol. 159, pp. 243-250, 2018/01 /2018 /01/doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.10.071>.
- [8] Y. Li *et al.*, "Optimal scheduling of isolated microgrid with an electric vehicle battery swapping station in multi-stakeholder scenarios: A bi-level programming approach via real-time pricing," *Applied Energy*, vol. 232, pp. 54-68, 2018/12/15/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.09.211>.
- [9] X. Lu, K. Zhou, S. Yang, and H. Liu, "Multi-objective optimal load dispatch of microgrid with stochastic access of electric vehicles," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 195, pp. 187-199, 2018/09/10/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.190>.
- [10] M. Sedighzadeh, M. Esmaili, and N. Mohammadkhani, "Stochastic multi-objective energy management in residential microgrids with combined cooling, heating, and power units considering battery energy storage systems and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 195, pp. 301-317, 2018/09/10/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.103>.
- [11] V .S. Tabar, M. A. Jirdehi, and R. Hemmati, "Energy management in microgrid based on the multi objective stochastic programming incorporating portable renewable energy resource as demand response option," *Energy*, vol. 118, pp. 827-839, 2017/01/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.10.113>.
- [12] J. Pascual, J. Barricarte, P. Sanchis, and L. Marroyo, "Energy management strategy for a renewable-based residential microgrid with generation and demand forecasting," *Applied Energy*, vol. 158, pp. 12- ,2015 /15/11/2015 ,25doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.08.040>.

-
-
- [13] P. Sreedharan, J. Farbes, E. Cutter, C. K. Woo, and J. Wang, "Microgrid and renewable generation integration: University of California, San Diego," *Applied Energy*, vol. 169, pp. 709-720, 2016/05/01/ 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.02.053>.
- [14] M. Nemati, M. Braun, and S. Tenbohlen, "Optimization of unit commitment and economic dispatch in microgrids based on genetic algorithm and mixed integer linear programming," *Applied Energy*, vol. 210, pp. 944-963, 2018/01/15/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.07.007>.
- [15] M. Abedini, M. H. Moradi, and S. M. Hosseinian, "Optimal management of microgrids including renewable energy sources using GPSO-GM algorithm," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 90, pp. 430-439, 2016/05/01/ 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.01.014>.
- [16] B. P. Numbi and S. J. Malinga, "Optimal energy cost and economic analysis of a residential grid-interactive solar PV system- case of eThekweni municipality in South Africa," *Applied Energy*, vol. 186, pp. 28-45, 2017/01/15/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.10.048>.
- [17] S. G. M. Rokni, M. Radmehr, and A. Zakariazadeh, "Optimum energy resource scheduling in a microgrid using a distributed algorithm framework," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 37, pp. 222-231, 2018/02/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.11.016>.
- [18] T. Kerdpol, F. S. Rahman, Y. Mitani, M. Watanabe, and S. K. Küfeoğlu, "Robust Virtual Inertia Control of an Islanded Microgrid Considering High Penetration of Renewable Energy," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 625-636, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2773486.
- [19] S. Gholami, S. Saha, and M. Aldeen, "Robust multiobjective control method for power sharing among distributed energy resources in islanded microgrids with unbalanced and nonlinear loads," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 94, pp. 321-338, 2018/01/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2017.07.012>.
- [20] A. L. Galindo Noguera, L. S. Mendoza Castellanos, E. E. Silva Lora, and V. R. Melian Cobas, "Optimum design of a hybrid diesel-ORC / photovoltaic system using PSO: Case study for the city of Cujubim, Brazil," *Energy*, vol. 142, pp. 33-45, 2018/01/01/ ,2018 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.10.012>.
- [21] J. Jung and M. Villaran, "Optimal planning and design of hybrid renewable energy systems for microgrids," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 75, pp. 180-191, 2017/08/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.10.061>.
- [22] H. Fathabadi, "Utilizing solar and wind energy in plug-in hybrid electric vehicles," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 156, pp. 317-328, 2018/01/15/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.11.015>
- [23] M. A. Zehir *et al.*, "Impacts of microgrids with renewables on secondary distribution networks," *Applied Energy*, vol. 201, pp. 308-319, 2017/09/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.12.138>.
- [24] M. Pesaran H.A, P. D. Huy, and V. K. Ramachandaramurthy, "A review of the optimal allocation of distributed generation: Objectives, constraints, methods, and algorithms," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 75, pp. 293-312, 2017/08/01/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.10.071>.
- [25] Y.-Y. Hong, W.-C. Chang, Y.-R. Chang, Y.-D. Lee, and D.-C. Ouyang, "Optimal sizing of renewable energy generations in a community microgrid using Markov model," *Energy*, vol. 135, pp. 68-74, 2017/09/15/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.06.098>.
- [26] N. Nikmehr, S. Najafi-Ravadanegh, and A. Khodaei, "Probabilistic optimal scheduling of networked microgrids considering time-based demand response programs under uncertainty," *Applied Energy*, vol. 198, pp. 267-279, 2017/07/15 ,2017 /doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.071>.
- [27] G. R. Aghajani, H. A. Shayanfar, and H. Shayeghi, "Demand side management in a smart microgrid in the presence of renewable generation and demand response," *Energy*, vol. 126, pp. 622-637, ,2017 /01/05/2017doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.051>.

-
-
- [28] M. Jalali, K. Zare, and H. Seyedi, "Strategic decision-making of distribution network operator with multi-microgrids considering demand response program," *Energy*, vol. 141, pp. 1059-1071, 2017/15/12/2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.09.145>.
- [29] G. R. Aghajani, H. A. Shayanfar, and H. Shayeghi, "Presenting a multi-objective generation scheduling model for pricing demand response rate in micro-grid energy management," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 106, pp. 308-321, 2015/12/01/ 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.08.059>.
- [30] M. H. Amrollahi and S. M. T. Bathaee, "Techno-economic optimization of hybrid photovoltaic/wind generation together with energy storage system in a stand-alone micro-grid subjected to demand response," *Applied Energy*, vol. 202, pp. 66-77, 2017/09/15/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.05.116>.
- [31] S. Bahramara and H. Golpîra, "Robust optimization of micro-grids operation problem in the presence of electric vehicles," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 37, pp. 388-395, 2018/02/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.11.039>.
- [32] H. Kamankesh, V. G. Agelidis, and A. Kavousi-Fard, "Optimal scheduling of renewable micro-grids considering plug-in hybrid electric vehicle charging demand," *Energy*, vol. 100, pp. 285-297, 2016/04/01/ 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.01.063>.
- [33] Y. R. Rodrigues, A. C. Zambroni de Souza, and P. F. Ribeiro, "An inclusive methodology for Plug-in electrical vehicle operation with G2V and V2G in smart microgrid environments," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 102, pp. 312-323, 2018/11/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2018.04.037>.
- [34] M. Shamshirband, J. Salehi, and F. S. Gazijahani, "Decentralized trading of plug-in electric vehicle aggregation agents for optimal energy management of smart renewable penetrated microgrids with the aim of CO2 emission reduction," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 200, pp. 622-640, 2018/11/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.315>.
- [35] E. Mortaz, A. Vinel, and Y. Dvorkin, "An optimization model for siting and sizing of vehicle-to-grid facilities in a microgrid," *Applied Energy*, vol. 242, pp. 1649-1660, 2019/05/15/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.03.131>.
- [36] A. Forati, S. Soleimani, F. Karimipour, and M. Malek, "INCLUDING USERS' SEMANTICS IN EVALUATING THE CREDIBILITY OF CROWDSOURCED LANDSCAPE DESCRIPTIONS," *The International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. 40, no. 3, p. 35, 2015.
- [37] Y. He, K. M. Kockelman, and K. A. Perrine, "Optimal locations of U.S. fast charging stations for long-distance trip completion by battery electric vehicles," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 214, pp. 452-461, 2019/03/20/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.188>.
- [38] P. Machura and Q. Li, "A critical review on wireless charging for electric vehicles," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 104, pp. 209-234, 2019/04/01/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.01.027>.
- [39] N. S. Pearre and L. G. Swan, "Electric vehicle charging to support renewable energy integration in a capacity constrained electricity grid," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 109, pp. 130-139, 2016/02/01/ 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.11.066>.
- [40] F. Baccino, S. Grillo, S. Massucco, and F. Silvestro, "A Two-Stage Margin-Based Algorithm for Optimal Plug-in Electric Vehicles Scheduling," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 759-766, 2015, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2014.2380826.
- [41] Y. He, B. Venkatesh, and L. Guan, "Optimal Scheduling for Charging and Discharging of Electric Vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1095-1105, 2012, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2011.2173507.
- [42] E. Sortomme and M. A. El-Sharkawi, "Optimal Scheduling of Vehicle-to-Grid Energy and Ancillary Services," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 351-359, 2012, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2011.2164099.

-
-
- [43] C. Wu, A. Mohammadi, M. Mehrtash, and A. Kargarian, "Non-Parametric Joint Chance Constraints for Economic Dispatch Problem with Solar Generation," in *2019 IEEE Texas Power and Energy Conference (TPEC)*, 7-8 Feb. 2019 2019, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/TPEC.2019.8662145.
- [44] Z. Liu, Y. Chen, R. Zhuo, and H. Jia, "Energy storage capacity optimization for autonomy microgrid considering CHP and EV scheduling," *Applied Energy*, vol. 210, pp. 1113-1125, 2018 ,2018 /15/01/doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.07.002>.
- [45] B. Odetayo, M. Kazemi, J. MacCormack, W. D. Rosehart, H. Zareipour, and A. R. Seifi, "A Chance Constrained Programming Approach to the Integrated Planning of Electric Power Generation , Natural Gas Network and Storage," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 6883-6893, 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2833465.
- [46] A. Soroudi, *Power system optimization modeling in GAMS*. Springer, 2017.
- [47] J. Jannati and D. Nazarpour, "Optimal energy management of the smart parking lot under demand response program in the presence of the electrolyser and fuel cell as hydrogen storage system," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 138, pp. 659-669, 2017/04/15/ 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.02.030>.